

Temple-Church of Aphrodisias

also known as “Basilica of Aphrodisias”

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Entry tags: Asia Minor, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Aegean, Graeco-Roman, Ancient Mediterranean, Abrahamic, Archaeological Site, Archaeological monument, Christian Traditions, Greek Religions, Early Christianity, Early Christianity, Temple, Basilica, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex, Cathedral

Aphrodisias is a UNESCO World Heritage site located near modern Geyre in southwestern Turkey. Although prehistoric human activity is attested at the site, the city proper was founded in the late 2nd or early 1st century BCE, rising up around the sanctuary of Aphrodite, the city's namesake goddess. Aphrodisias became part of the Roman Empire in the late 1st century BCE and enjoyed a period of growth and prosperity. In the 3rd century CE, the city became capital of the province of Caria, which was followed by a building boom. A small Christian presence existed in Aphrodisias by the end of the 3rd century CE, as a number of martyrs are attested from around the year 300. By 325, the city had its own bishop. Around the year 500 (dated from coins excavated from the foundation of the outer narthex), the temple of Aphrodite was converted into a Christian church. The temple was essentially turned 'inside out': the cella walls were dismantled and rebuilt as the outer walls of the church, supplemented with spolia from elsewhere in the city. The columns from the eastern and western colonnades were moved to align with the north and south rows, creating a large tripartite church with an apse to the east and narthexes at the west. This conversion was a massive physical and logistical effort, undertaken in a systematic, strategic, and precise manner-- column drums from the east and west colonnades were labeled for their exact re-erection. In the 10th or 11th century, the church was renovated: new floors were laid, a small chapel was constructed in the north aisle, a new sanctuary barrier was installed, and new paintings of Christ, Mary, archangels, saints/martyrs, and crosses were added in the synthronon passageway. The church was ultimately destroyed by fire in the late 12th century, likely a casualty of ongoing Seljuk raids in the Maeander valley. The archaeological evidence indicates that it remained in use until its destruction.

Date Range: 450 CE - 1199 CE

Region: Aphrodisias, temple-church

Region tags: Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Turkey, Anatolia, Byzantium

The extent of the temple-church at Aphrodisias

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1904-present

Notes: The site has been known to European travelers since the early 18th century. Various expeditions came to record and sketch inscriptions and monuments, but the first excavation was not conducted until 1904, when a French team led by Paul Gaudin and Gustave Mendel excavated the temple and the nearby Hadrianic baths.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Aphrodisias Excavations

Notes: New York University has conducted excavations on the site since 1961 under the aegis of the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism. Since 1995 the excavations have also been conducted with the collaboration of Oxford University.

Reference: Aphrodisias Excavations Project. “Aphrodisias Excavations”. Project website, 2019. <http://aphrodisias.classics.ox.ac.uk/index.html>.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Mountain

Notes: The temple-church is not oriented according to the orthogonal city grid, but rather (as Sitz 2019 argues) to align with the summit of a nearby prominent mountain.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The Temple of Aphrodite was surrounded by an ornate temenos wall, demarcating a large open area likely used for cult activity and ritual. There was also a forecourt to the east, entered through a monumental propylon.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The temple-church is rectangular, measuring approximately 60 by 30.5 meters in area. There is a roughly rectangular outer narthex appended to the west side of the building.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The temple-church itself was adapted from the earlier temple of Aphrodite. To convert the temple, the temple's cella walls were dismantled and rebuilt as the outer walls of the church, supplemented with spolia from elsewhere. The columns from the eastern and western temple colonnades were moved to align with the north and south rows of columns. The result is a large tripartite church with an apse to the east and narthexes at the west. In the 10th or 11th century, the church was refurbished: new floors were laid, a small chapel was constructed in the north aisle, a new sanctuary barrier was installed, and new paintings of Christ, Mary, archangels, saints, and crosses were added in the synthronon passageway.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Reference: Aphrodisias Excavations Project. "Aphrodisias Excavations". Project website, 2019. <http://aphrodisias.classics.ox.ac.uk/index.html>.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

– As the result of pillage

Notes: The church was most likely deliberately burnt down in the Seljuk

conquest of the region in the late 12th century.

Reference: Aphrodisias Excavations Project. "Aphrodisias Excavations". Project website, 2019. <http://aphrodisias.classics.ox.ac.uk/index.html>.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to the worship of the Christian God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: There is no dedicatory inscription indicating if a local elite/elites were directly responsible for commissioning the temple-church; however, the conversion of the temple into a church was a massive effort that would have required a dedicated and organized workforce, likely charged by local civic and ecclesiastical elites.

Reference: Sitz, Anna M.. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Epigraphic Reuse in the Temple-church at Aphrodisias" 12, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jla.2019.0006>.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence to indicate who exactly did the construction work, but the conversion of the temple into a church would have required specialized, skilled laborers. There is a fragmentary graffito with the word οικοδομοι (builders) on one of the column bases, though the date and context is uncertain.

Reference: Sitz, Anna M.. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Epigraphic Reuse in the Temple-church at Aphrodisias" 12, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jla.2019.0006>.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no dedicatory inscription indicating if any person or group of people was directly responsible for financial and material contributions.

Reference: Sitz, Anna M.. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Epigraphic Reuse in the Temple-church at Aphrodisias" 12, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jla.2019.0006>.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1830

Notes: Structure measures approximately 60 x 30.5 meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the building's destruction, its height is unknown.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1830

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Reference: Hebert, Laura. "The Temple-church at Aphrodisias", 2000.

<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/temple-church-at-aphrodisias/docview/304608527/se-2>.

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Mortar which attached decorative elements to the walls has been excavated.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Charcoal was excavated that may have belonged to the timbers of the roof. Hebert (2000: 46) hypothesizes that the roof was constructed of wooden beams, upon which terracotta roof tiles rested.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: Some fragments of decorative revetment made from nonlocal, imported stone (such as Egyptian and Laconian porphyry) were excavated from the interior of the church.

– Yes

Notes: The temple-church was constructed entirely of white marble. Aphrodisias is known for the proximity of fine marble quarries nearby.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Terracotta

Notes: The roof was covered in terracotta tiles.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Reference: Hebert, Laura. "The Temple-church at Aphrodisias", 2000.

<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/temple-church-at-aphrodisias/docview/304608527/se-2>.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Glass mosaic tesserae were excavated from the interior of the church, indicating that the ceiling or clerestory was covered in a decorative mosaic scheme. The floor was also covered in a geometric mosaic pattern.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: There are figural paintings that date to the church's renovation in the Middle Byzantine period. There is a possibility that there were other permanent or non-permanent figural decorative elements in the temple-church, but due to the building's destruction none have been discerned.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus, the human form of the Christian God, is depicted in a Middle Byzantine wall painting.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Archangels are depicted in a Middle Byzantine wall painting.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: John the Baptist and various saints/martyrs/monks are depicted in a Middle Byzantine wall painting.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There is a partially preserved floor mosaic in a geometric pattern.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is a wall painting of a jeweled cross dated to the Middle Byzantine period.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a possibility that some decorative elements in the temple-church were

restricted, but due to the building's destruction it is impossible to tell.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: No statue fragments were excavated from the debris.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Geometric and cross patterns

Notes: A fragment of a marble chancel screen with a geometric pattern was excavated and restored to its original position. Additionally, nine epistyle blocks dating to the Middle Byzantine renovation of the church were found, bearing geometric motifs and crosses.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: The temple-church was renovated in the Middle Byzantine period and wall paintings were added in the passageway behind the synthronon. The paintings depict Jesus and Mary flanked by angels, saints, and John the Baptist, as well as jeweled crosses. For a detailed description of the paintings, see Hebert (2000): 224-230.

Reference: Hebert, Laura. "The Temple-church at Aphrodisias", 2000.
<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/temple-church-at-aphrodisias/docview/304608527/se-2>.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is a possibility that some of the above motifs existed in the mosaic decorations, but due to the building's destruction it is impossible to know.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Reference: Sitz, Anna M.. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Epigraphic Reuse in the Temple-church at Aphrodisias" 12, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jla.2019.0006>.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: The church was constructed from spolia taken from the original temple of Aphrodite and other older structures in the city. Many of these blocks bear numerous graffiti and inscriptions. Some refer to Aphrodite, her temple, and her priests; others are dedications to Augustus; Christian monograms and crosses also proliferate, some of which may have been intentional elements of the decorative scheme while others were likely graffiti. Sitz (2019) argues that older inscriptions were deliberately incorporated into the church to create a "visual synkrisis between the old and the new."

Reference: Sitz, Anna M.. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Epigraphic Reuse in the Temple-church at Aphrodisias" 12, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jla.2019.0006>.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There are dedicatory inscriptions belonging to earlier centuries/buildings on the spoliated blocks that comprise the temple-church; however, there is no dedicatory inscription for the temple-church itself.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There are paintings of the archangels.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: There are paintings that may depict saints and/or martyrs who are deceased; whether this constitutes a portrayal of the afterlife is up for debate.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Although the building's primary function was for worship, several burials have been excavated from in and around the temple-church. Two burials that probably date to the conversion period have also been excavated from beneath the church floor, one near the center of the south aisle and the other in the northeastern corner of the nave, though both have been disturbed by looters. Many more burials dating to the Middle Byzantine period were excavated, both from within the church's atrium and in the temenos area surrounding the church.

Reference: Hebert, Laura. "The Temple-church at Aphrodisias", 2000.

<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/temple-church-at-aphrodisias/docview/304608527/se-2>.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– I don't know

Notes: The 'presence' of the Christian God in church spaces is a huge question and depends upon how one views the nuances of doctrinal and theological literature. I have selected 'I don't know' for this question to acknowledge the ambiguity inherent.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian God can be said to communicate with visitors through prayer and worship

activities.

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– No

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Are previously human spirits present:
– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– I don't know

Notes: Again, the 'I don't know' reflects the ambiguity of how one might view Jesus, the human aspect of God.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: I take communication in this question to refer to prayer, addressed to God, Mary, and saints/martyrs.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that there were votive offerings given as a part of the liturgy or left by pilgrims/visitors, but none have been excavated or identified as such.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– I don't know

Notes: Likely, the priests or bishops performed some kind of regular maintenance activities, but no material evidence for this survives.

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There is substantial evidence for the periodic repair and renovation of the temple-church, particularly a major renovation occurring in the Middle Byzantine period.

Reference: Hebert, Laura. "The Temple-church at Aphrodisias", 2000.
<https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/temple-church-at-aphrodisias/docview/304608527/se-2>.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Notes: Again, it is likely that the priests or bishops performed some kind of regular maintenance activities, but no material evidence for this survives.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: No festivals per se were held, but liturgical holidays and processions were likely held in and around the church.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Healing is not a primary function for this church, but the possibility that visitors came with the hope of receiving healing cannot be ruled out.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: E.g. mass, processions, possibly baptisms (although no baptistery has been found), funerals

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown, though see Hebert (2000), pgs. 165-172 for a discussion of the possible seating/standing arrangements of the interior space.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Mass/the Eucharistic liturgy: at least weekly; baptisms and funerals: when necessary

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes

- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes

Notes: Bishops and priests were male, but it is possible that female clergy were present for baptismal rituals for female catechumens (for example).

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No

- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
 - Yes

Notes: Access to the sanctuary at the eastern end of the church was physically restricted by chancel screens and very likely reserved for clergy.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The nearby Triconch House (also known as the Bishop's Palace) is hypothesized to have housed the church's bishop starting in the Middle Byzantine period, but it is not physically proximate to the temple-church itself.

Reference: Berenfeld, Michelle. *The Triconch House*. Wiesbaden: Reichert Verlag, 2019.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Aphrodisias was an official bishopric of the Church, so was subject to the institutions of the overarching ecclesiastical body.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: There is a possibility that non-religious writing was stored here, but due to the building's destruction it is unknown.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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